

**Enhancing Security at the Physical Layer of Wireless
Systems: Applications in Code-Domain NOMA**

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Preliminaries

WDRF50

SUSTAINABILITY Goals

Quality Education • Clean Water and Sanitation • Gender Equality • Life Below Water • Life on Land • No Poverty • Good Health and Well-being • Climate Action • Sustainable Cities and Communities • Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions • Clean Water and Sanitation • Zero Hunger • Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure • Affordable and Clean Energy • Reduced Inequalities • Partnerships for the Goals • Responsible Consumption and Production • Decent Work and Economic Growth

6G HUMANITY

SOCIETAL Challenges

Education Innovations • Societal Services • Health and Wellbeing Services • Urbanisation vs. Remote • Infrastructure • Work Life Change • Data Security and Privacy • Automation • Personalisation

TECHNOLOGY Enablers

RAN Agnostic/Automatically Orchestrated Transceivers • Non-device Centric Communications HBI • Extreme URLLC • Below CM Positioning • Consent and Privacy Preserving Data Sharing • Support for Ambient/Novel Sensing • Small Data AI (Distributed Learning) • Distributed Trust • Cyber-physical Security • Terahertz Technologies • 4D-Imaging and Image Projection and XR • Haptic Remote Telepresence • Full Spectrum Photonic Signal Processing • Proactive Decision Making/Informations Offering • Pervasive User Identification and Authentication • Net Neutrality • Zero-energy Communications • AI Inspired Air Interfaces • Grant Free Access (IoT)

PRODUCTIVITY in Vertical Industries

Health • Manufacturing • Finance Technologies • Society 5.0 • Transport • Global Affordable Coverage • Education • Agriculture • Energy • FinTech

Preliminaries

WDRF50

New Hardware and Physical Layer Technologies

Source: 6G Flagship

Limitations of a wireless network

- Open wireless access medium
- Limited bandwidth
- System complexity
- Limited power
- Limited processing capacity

Traditional methods for providing security in wireless networks are not adequate (in some emerging scenarios) due to the low computational capabilities of some devices.

Physical Layer Security (PLS)

PLS leverages radio propagation physics' fundamental capacity to provide certain types of security, at the physical layer level.

Reliability

Bob can decode the message transmitted by Alice without error (perfect reliability).

$$P(\hat{M} = M) \rightarrow 1$$

Secrecy

Eve does not obtain information from the message transmitted from Alice to Bob (perfect secrecy).

$$I(Z, M) \rightarrow 0$$

The symbol \rightarrow implies different definitions (metrics), which can lead to different levels of reliability or secrecy.

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access

Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA).

There is no interference among users within the same cell.

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) is employed in 4G (LTE) networks.

Non-orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA).

There is interference among users within the same cell.

The interference can be mitigated using multi-user detectors at the receiver.

It is an interesting option for IoT wireless networks.

There are two proposals:

- Power domain NOMA (P-NOMA).
- Code domain NOMA (C-NOMA).

Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA).

Non-orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA).

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access

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Sparse Code Multiple Access

Hosein Nikopour and Hadi Baligh
Ottawa Wireless R&D Centre
Huawei Technologies Canada Co., LTD.

Different bit strings are directly assigned codewords that belong to different books of multidimensional codes.

- These codebooks are obtained using the signal space diversity technique.
- Each codebook is assigned to a different user.

SCMA allows system overload.

Multiuser Detector based on the Belief Propagation algorithm: Message Passing Algorithm (MPA).

- Nearly-optimal low-complexity detector.

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access

Transmission

16-point SCMA
 $J = 6$ users
 $K = 4$ subcarriers
 $N = 2$ subcarriers

PLS Application in C-NOMA

IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON VEHICULAR TECHNOLOGY

Secure Transmission for Uplink SCMA Systems Over κ - μ Fading Channels

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Rotation Matrices

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & -z & -w \\ -y & x & w & -z \\ z & w & x & y \\ -w & z & -y & x \end{bmatrix},$$

where $x = (u\sqrt{1 + \lambda_2^2})^{-1}$, $y = \lambda_2(u\sqrt{1 + \lambda_2^2})^{-1}$, $z = \lambda_4(u\lambda_2)^{-1}$, $w = \lambda_4 u^{-1}$, with $u = \lambda_2^{-1} \sqrt{\lambda_2^2 + \lambda_4^4 + \lambda_2 \lambda_4^2}$, where λ_2 and λ_4 are the rotation parameters (RPs).

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Metric proportional to the BER

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_i \sum_j \prod_{d=1}^D \left(\frac{c_{i \rightarrow j, d}^2}{\mu_d(1 + \kappa_d)} \right)^{-\mu_d}$$

The best rotation parameters can be found for each user.

This metric depends on the fading channel parameters and the rotation parameters.

Each user may have different rotation parameters because their channels experience independent fading.

Metric \mathcal{L} as a function of λ_2 and λ_4 considering $\kappa = 0.5$ and $\mu = 3$.

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Small databases are generated with a group of \mathcal{R}_t rotation parameters based on the channel estimation performed by the BS and the LUTs.

Errors in channel estimation can lead to different rotation parameters, but strategies to minimize this error were also proposed.

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The rotation parameters are selected based on a secret key derived from the random phases of the wireless channel, which are unique for each user.

PDF of the random channel phase θ for different values of κ and μ .

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The secret keys are used as initial parameters to generate chaotic sequences (via tent map or logistic map), which are used to select the rotation parameters for each user.

This prevents eavesdroppers from determining the rotation parameters used, even in the worst-case scenario where it has knowledge of databases with such parameters.

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BER of Legitimate Users at the BS (Uncoded System)

Optimal λ_2, λ_4 for κ - μ fading.

Non-optimal λ_2, λ_4 for κ - μ fading.

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Secure Transmission for Uplink SCMA Systems Over κ - μ Fading Channels

BER of Legitimate Users at the BS and at the Eavesdropper
considering channel estimation errors (Turbo encoded System)

(a) $\sigma_e^2 = 0$.

(b) $\sigma_e^2 = 10^{-4}$.

(c) $\sigma_e^2 = 10^{-3}$.

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NOMA's ability to efficiently serve multiple users on the same radio resource is especially beneficial for IoT networks, where a massive number of devices need to communicate simultaneously.

PLS in IoT devices with limited computational capabilities provides robust protection by leveraging wireless channel characteristics, reducing computational overhead, and enhancing security without relying heavily on complex cryptographic processes.

The idea for obtaining PLS in SCMA systems lies in generating codebooks for each user that are unknown to the eavesdropper. The generation of these codebooks must ensure good system performance without imposing a high computational burden on the involved devices.

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